

THE UNIQUE FEATURES OF THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

Alijonov Bakhtiyor Khoshimovich

Independent Researcher of
Fergana state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10427633>

Abstract: According to the experience of states that have rapidly and significantly developed in social progress, each nation, by setting lofty and purposeful goals for itself and utilizing the capabilities to achieve and implement them, occupies a relevant place in the global community. The modern states aim to ensure harmony and stability in society, providing effective protection of human rights and freedoms. The current development of our country is characterized by prioritizing peace and stability, as well as creating conditions for mutual respect and a peaceful environment among nations.

Keywords: social development, social system, stability, moral-ethical, civilizational development, spiritual values, national pride, cultural heritage, history of statehood, education, justice.

The strategy of development is based on the mentality of our people, which is expressed by the desire for enlightenment, education, justice, morality, honesty and is based on high spirituality. The global changes that have occurred at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century have introduced significant transformations into the current economic thinking and the trends of social and economic development. It is well-known from history that a country cannot ensure its national interests without considering the economic development and the prosperity of its people. Various foreign countries have adapted their development models according to their specific conditions, indicating instances of improvement in some countries under the framework of the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States), external debt reduction, and the conditions of the world financial and economic crisis, revealing their weaknesses. In the early 20th century, countries shaped their economic development based on the models of America and Europe, while after the Second World War, models specific to Germany and Japan emerged. Similarly, the countries of Asia and Africa that have achieved independence have adopted paths influenced by various models. However, the experience of these countries proves that it is not always possible to straightforwardly accept the development path of another country. In the governance of the state and society, a system has been established that is based on transparency and justice, allowing for the adoption of people-oriented decisions that serve the interests of

the population. Most importantly, we have modified the long-standing "state-society-human" concept that has been in practice for many years[1; 5-p.].

On a global scale, the establishment of an intercultural and democratic society is considered one of the fundamental principles. According to the experience of states that have achieved rapid and substantial social development, each nation attains a significant and influential position globally by setting lofty and progressive goals and utilizing the capabilities to realize them on the world stage. The contemporary nations aim to ensure social stability and sustainability while effectively safeguarding human rights and freedoms. Today, the primary focus of our country's development is to create the conditions necessary for progress, peace, and stability, fostering intercultural harmony, and providing the circumstances and opportunities for peaceful coexistence. In the new Uzbekistan, the philosophical principles of developing a society based on national policies, advancing the development of a civilized society with mutual respect, trust, and the decision to create a democratic, strong civil society and ensure political stability have gained great importance.

"Most importantly, the strengthening of the statehood, which ensures the advancement of the republic to the ranks of economically developed countries, characterized by social justice, definiteness, and precision in market relations, efficient utilization of collective potential and resources, and the sustainable development of the people's welfare, requires comprehensive improvements" [2; 278-b.]. The essence and objectives of reforms, as well as their specific features tailored to the unique characteristics of the population, are visible to a broad audience. The strategy of democratic reforms implemented in our country determines the final goal of our chosen path.

The fundamental directions of reforms that will be implemented in the new era of the development of our country are outlined as follows:

- "First – Elevating the status of a people-oriented state through the development of a free civil society and the enhancement of human values.
- Second – Advancing the establishment of justice and the rule of law as the most essential and necessary conditions for the progress of our country.
- Third – Modernizing the national economy and accelerating its growth in line with contemporary requirements.
- Forth – Pursuing a just social policy to develop human capital.

- Fifth – Ensuring spiritual development, reforming this sphere comprehensively, and stepping into a new stage.
- Sixth – Addressing global challenges that humanity and our people face in today's world.
- Seventh – Enhancing the security and defense capability of our country, adopting an open and pragmatic, active foreign policy; [3; 10-p.]”.

Every nation, country, and people live their lives based on specific principles and values established by their social systems and state, and they pursue their interests, aspirations, and goals while moving forward. Each country and people, in the course of their historical and social development, evolves in line with defined ideals and aspirations. In our state, which is built on social cooperation, freedom, and a democratic society, the national ideology consolidates all layers of the population, directing them towards collective goals and common interests. This ideology excludes confrontational approaches and instead fosters universal human development. Every ideology sets specific goals for itself. These goals determine the ways, means, and methods to achieve the desired outcome.

Uzbekistan's engagement with the global community is characterized by, above all, friendly cooperation with neighboring states, mutual support, and collaboration for strength, peace, security, tranquility, and progress. The society's development is based on spiritual, ethical, and cultural advancements, nurturing moral values, national pride, cultural heritage, the history of the Uzbek people and statehood, and ensuring the provision of comprehensive education, fostering the upbringing of harmoniously developed generations, and promoting prosperity.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "Human dignity, for his rights and freedoms, legal benefits." – Tashkent: "Uzbekistan," 2022.
2. Karimov I.A. Homeland is as sacred as a place of worship. T. 3. - T., 1996.
3. Makhmudovna, A. Sh. (2022/3/4).creative writing in grammar lessons. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 258-260
4. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/3/4).Working with Texts in Grammar Lessons.barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali,261-263
5. Makhmudovna, A. Sh.(2022/11/15).Lexical-Semantic Classification of Concepts Related to Wedding and Marriage,(11)146-149
6. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "New Uzbekistan Development Strategy." – Tashkent: "Uzbekistan," 2022.

7. I. Karimov. "Ensuring security, conditions of stability, and development guarantees in Uzbekistan in the 21st century." – Tashkent: "Uzbekistan," 1997.
8. <https://religions.uz/news/detail?id=634>
9. Siddikov, I., & Gulomov, A. (2020). Philosophical and psychological features of the formation of asertive behavior in the development of cognitive activity. In Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества (pp. 38-42).
10. Abdinazarovich, R. D., Abdullajonovna, Y. K., Ahadjanovich, Q. A., Bakhromovich, G. A., & Juraevna, N. N. (2020). The role of social service in the protection of human interests. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(6), 1263-1267.
11. Gulomov, A. (2019). Participation and role of uzbekistan in finding solutions to global environmental problems. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 152-156.